

Universität Luzern, Fakultät für Gesundheitswissenschaften und Medizin

Dissertation unter der Betreuung von Prof. Dr. med. Christian Kamm
Luzerner Kantonsspital
Klinik für Neurologie und Neurorehabilitation

Characterizing post-COVID-19 Syndrome in Multiple Sclerosis: Vaccine Status, Infection Burden, and Therapy Categories as Predictors

DISSERTATION

Zur Erlangung der Doktorwürde der Humanmedizin (Dr. med.)
An der Fakultät für Gesundheitswissenschaften und Medizin
der Universität Luzern

Vorgelegt von
Dr. medic. (RO) Deepak Sharma

Dissertation genehmigt am 18. Dezember 2025

Publikationshinweis

Characterizing post-COVID-19 Syndrome in Multiple Sclerosis: Vaccine Status, Infection Burden, and Therapy Categories as Predictors

Publiziert am: 11. Oktober 2025

Journal: Multiple Sclerosis and related disorders (MSARD)
DOI: [10.1016/j.msard.2025.106792](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msard.2025.106792)

Publikation

Characterizing post-COVID-19 Syndrome in Multiple Sclerosis: Vaccine Status, Infection Burden, and Therapy Categories as Predictors

Deepak Sharma¹ [ORCID: 0009-0007-9042-0189], Christian P. Kamm^{1, 2} [ORCID: 0000-0002-3906-0161], Robert Hoepner² [ORCID: 0000-0002-0115-7021], Iris-Katharina Penner [ORCID: 0000-0002-6746-1034], Thomas Nyffeler¹ [ORCID: 0000-0003-2504-8935], Lara Diem¹ [ORCID: 0000-0001-6171-5761]

¹ Department of Neurology, Luzerner Kantonsspital, Lucerne, Switzerland

² Department of Neurology, Inselspital, Bern University Hospital, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Lara Diem

Department of Neurology

Luzerner Kantonsspital

Spitalstrasse

6000 Luzern 16, Switzerland

Email: [lara.diem@luks.ch]

Word Count: 3764 (Main Text)

Abstract Word Count: 250

Number of Tables/Figures: 3

Number of References: 22

Keywords:

post-COVID-19 Syndrome; Multiple Sclerosis; Disease-Modifying Therapies; Vaccination; Long COVID; SARS-CoV-2; Fatigue

Short Running Title:

post-COVID-19 Risk Factors in MS

Abstract

Background: Post-COVID-19 syndrome (PCS) is a significant long-term complication of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) infection, yet its prevalence and risk factors in people with multiple sclerosis (pwMS) under disease-modifying therapies (DMTs) remain underexplored.

Objective: This study aimed to characterize the clinical course of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) and identify predictors of PCS in pwMS, focusing on vaccination status, infection severity and frequency, and DMT categories.

Methods: In this cross-sectional study, 107 pwMS from two centers completed a survey assessing COVID-19 history, persistent symptoms, immunotherapy, and vaccination status. PCS was defined as symptoms persisting >12 weeks after infection. Participants were stratified by DMT categories, infection number, and vaccination status.

Results: Of 107 participants, 7 (6.5%) reported PCS. The most frequent symptoms were fatigue (71.4%), pain (57.1%), and headache (42.9%). Patients with PCS had a higher mean number of SARS-CoV-2 infections (2.1, 95% CI: 1.3–3.0) compared to those without (1.3, 95% CI: 1.2–1.4; $p = 0.004$). A significant association was found with DMT category: 71.4% (5/7) of affected individuals were on category I therapies (Interferon/Glatiramer acetate, Dimethyl fumarate, Teriflunomide) compared to 17% of pwMS without PCS ($p < 0.001$). No significant effect was observed for COVID-19 severity or vaccination status.

Conclusions: PCS prevalence in this MS cohort was lower than in the general population, but category I DMTs and repeated infections were key risk factors. Findings suggest the need for individualized risk assessment and a possible protective effect of higher efficacy DMTs against PCS in pwMS.

1. Introduction

Post-COVID-19 Syndrome

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, caused by the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), has led to unprecedented global health crises and has significantly strained healthcare systems worldwide. While the acute phase of COVID-19 has been the primary focus of medical interventions, there is growing recognition of a condition known as post-COVID-19 Syndrome (PCS), which affects a substantial number of individuals who have recovered from the initial infection (Montani et al., 2022; Nalbandian et al., 2021; Pierce et al., 2022).

According to the World Health Organization, PCS is defined as “the continuation or development of new symptoms 3 months after the initial SARS-CoV-2 infection, with these symptoms lasting for at least 2 months with no other explanation” (Post

COVID-19 Condition (Long COVID), n.d.). This syndrome has become a significant global concern, with various studies reporting different prevalence rates based on symptom duration.

Notably, prevalence rates have declined over the course of the pandemic, driven by widespread immunization, prior infections, and the reduced pathogenicity of newer variants such as Omicron. Early pandemic estimates ranged from 10% to 15%, with some studies reporting up to 40% (Chen et al., 2022, Ford ND et al. 2022), whereas current estimates are generally lower, often between 7.3% and 16.5%. These overlapping results emphasize the persistence of PCS symptoms across diverse populations, contributing to a substantial long-term health burden.

A critical aspect of understanding PCS is identifying the risk factors that contribute to its development. These include demographic, clinical, and lifestyle factors. Female sex (odds ratio (OR) 1.56; 95% CI, 1.41-1.73) and older age (OR 1.21; 95% CI, 1.11-1.33) are associated with increased risk. Comorbidities such as depressive mood with feelings of anxiety, asthma, chronic kidney disease, diabetes, and immunosuppression further elevate susceptibility. Severe acute COVID-19, particularly cases requiring hospitalization (OR 2.48; 95% CI, 1.97-3.13) or intensive care unit (ICU) admission (OR 2.37; 95% CI, 2.18-2.56), substantially increases the likelihood of developing PCS. Additionally, high BMI (>25 kg/m²) (OR 1.15; 95% CI, 1.08-1.23), smoking (OR 1.10; 95% CI, 1.07-1.13), and socioeconomic factors contribute to this risk. In contrast, vaccination provides protective benefits, with two doses reducing the likelihood of PCS (OR 0.57; 95% CI, 0.43-0.76) (Tsampasian et al., 2023)

People with chronic conditions such as multiple sclerosis (MS) have faced unique challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic. MS is a chronic autoimmune disorder of the central nervous system, often requiring long-term immunosuppressive treatment (Kamm et al., 2014). The intersection of MS and COVID-19 raises important concerns regarding infection susceptibility, disease severity, and the potential for exacerbation of neurological symptoms.

Although initial studies suggested that COVID-19 does not alter the short-term course of MS, patients with MS appear more vulnerable to persistent symptoms, particularly fatigue, following SARS-CoV-2 infection compared to healthy individuals. Moreover, recent analyses suggest that in patients receiving certain immunotherapies—such as anti-CD20 monoclonal antibodies—the COVID-19-related mortality did not decline to the same extent as observed in the general population during the course of the vaccination campaign (Salmen et al., 2023). In summary, the combination of pre-existing neuropsychiatric issues, impaired stress coping, central fatigue mechanisms, and the negative psychosocial impact of the pandemic may make pwMS more vulnerable to persistent symptoms like fatigue after SARS-CoV-2 infection (Motolese et al., 2020). In some cases, COVID-19 has been associated with MS relapses or a worsening of existing symptoms, especially

in those receiving immunosuppressive therapies (Prosperini et al., 2024). Conversely, while MS does not appear to increase the severity of acute COVID-19 in most patients, certain DMTs, especially B-cell depleting agents, may impair immune response and prolong recovery (Bazylewicz et al., 2023). PCS, characterized by fatigue, cognitive impairment, and other lingering symptoms, poses a particular diagnostic and therapeutic challenge in MS, given the significant symptom overlap. While MS and PCS fatigue share some clinical features, they differ in intensity and triggers. PCS fatigue tends to be more severe, less relieved by rest, and more delayed, whereas MS fatigue is more sensitive to heat and mood changes (Oliver-Mas et al., 2025). While evidence points to an elevated risk of post-viral sequelae in immunosuppressed individuals, comprehensive data on the development and progression of PCS in MS remain scarce (Cervia et al., 2022; Tsampasian et al., 2023).

Among DMTs, anti-CD20 monoclonal antibodies such as ocrelizumab and rituximab have been repeatedly linked to more severe COVID-19 outcomes, including higher hospitalization and complication rates (Januel et al., 2023; Prosperini et al., 2024). Conversely, other DMTs may carry a lower risk, as some studies have reported reduced hospitalization rates in treated vs. untreated MS patients (Liu et al., 2023). Additional risk factors—such as older age, higher disability (EDSS), and comorbidities like cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and obesity, further compound vulnerability, independently from current treatment. These complex interrelations underscore the importance of individualized management strategies, including careful DMTs selection and optimized vaccination protocols.

Understanding how DMTs influence PCS trajectories is therefore critical to informing clinical decision-making in MS care (Wenzel et al., 2022).

In this study, we aim to characterize the clinical course of COVID-19 and PCS in a real-world cohort of people with multiple sclerosis (pwMS). Specifically, we assess whether different DMTs are associated with variations in acute disease severity and the risk of long-term symptoms. By elucidating these relationships, our goal is to inform risk-adapted therapeutic decisions—such as optimizing the choice or timing of DMTs—and to improve long-term outcomes for pwMS in the context of ongoing SARS-CoV-2 exposure.

2. Patients and Methods

We conducted an anonymous online survey, launched via Survey Monkey (<https://de.surveymonkey.com/>) to investigate the course of COVID-19 in pwMS and their risk to develop PCS. The survey was distributed via our MS consultation at the neurological outpatient departments of the Cantonal Hospital Lucerne in Lucerne and Department of Neurology, Inselspital, Bern University Hospital, Switzerland. Data were collected from 07/2024, to 01/2025. All respondents gave digital informed consent prior to participation. It is noteworthy that the questionnaires were solely handed out in the context of dedicated outpatient visits, allowing clinical verification of the MS diagnosis. This ensured that all participants included in the study met established diagnostic criteria for MS, thereby enhancing the validity of the cohort. Patients were able to report a confirmed history of SARS-CoV-2 infection based on either a positive polymerase chain reaction (PCR) test or a positive antibody test. The Ethics Committee of the north-western and central part of Switzerland (EKNZ) has approved the project (BASEC 2024-00517). The survey “Conditions of participation” stated in the German language for the patient: “You may participate in the study if the following applies to you: (1) COVID-19 acute illness occurred at least 12 weeks (3 months) ago. (2) You are diagnosed with Multiple Sclerosis. (3) You are at least 18 years old and have a sufficiently good knowledge of German to be able to complete this questionnaire.”

The survey consisted of 41 questions and 10 minutes were needed for completion. Our survey investigated the following 7 domains: demographic characteristics (8/41 questions), acute COVID-19 illness (11/41 questions), PCS (9/41 questions), therapy of PCS (1/41 questions), fatigue-syndrome (2/41 questions), Consequences of PCS on Everyday Life (2/41 questions), and vaccination (6/41 questions).

In total, 116 anonymized responses were downloaded from the Survey Monkey server. 9 incomplete responses, defined as more than 50% missing answers, were removed, leading to a data set of 107 responses. Data are presented as mean with 95% confidence interval (95% CI), comparative statistics were used, and type of testing is referred prior to each p-value. A p-value of 0.05 was assumed as significant. In case of multiple testing, a Bonferroni correction was run.

To examine factors associated with the occurrence of PCS, we performed multivariate logistic regression analysis. The dependent variable was the presence of PCS symptoms. The following independent variables were included as predictors: age, sex, vaccination status, reported number of SARS-CoV-2 infections, administration of antiviral therapy during acute infection, and presence of comorbidities.

Quantitative variables are described using the mean and 95% CI and they were compared with Mann Whitney Test. Qualitative variables are presented as absolute numbers and frequencies and were compared with Chi-squared. Adjustment for multiple testing was performed by Bonferroni procedure.

DMTs were categorized into three groups according to their efficacy: category I (low efficacy), category II (moderate efficacy), and category III (high efficacy). category I treatments included interferon-beta, glatiramer acetate, dimethyl fumarate, and teriflunomide, category II included sphingosine-1-phosphate receptor modulators and cladribine. category III included natalizumab and anti-CD20 monoclonal antibodies like ocrelizumab, ofatumumab and rituximab. A small subset of patients had also undergone autologous hematopoietic stem cell transplantation. These patients were included in Category III.

3. Results

3.1 Population characteristics & MS characteristics

Population characteristics

The study cohort had a mean age of 42.7 years (95% CI: 40.4-45.0, n=107), with a predominance of female patients (71/107, 66.4%). The most common comorbidities were cardiovascular diseases (9/107, 8.4%), followed by migraine (3/107, 2.8%), depression (3/107, 2.8%), and rheumatological diseases (3/107, 2.8%).

Regarding medications other than disease-modifying therapies, nearly half of the patients reported taking vitamin supplements (54/107, 50.5%), while antihypertensive drugs (11/107, 10.2%), antispasticity drugs (9/107, 8.4%), and lipid-lowering or antidiabetic therapy (5/107, 4.8% each) were also frequently used. Table 1 (section A1) provides a detailed overview.

MS characteristics

Among the study participants, the majority were diagnosed with relapsing-remitting multiple sclerosis (RRMS) (90/107, 84.1%), followed by primary progressive MS (PPMS) (12/107, 11.2%), secondary progressive MS (SPMS) (5/107, 4.7%).

The most used DMTs were anti-CD20 monoclonal antibodies (53/107, 49.5%), followed by dimethyl fumarate (17/107, 15.8%), sphingosine-1-phosphate receptor modulators (7/107, 6.5%), and cladribine or natalizumab (6/107, 5.6% each). Among the 7 patients who developed post-COVID-19 syndrome, 1 patient was treated with ocrelizumab, 5 patients with dimethyl fumarate, and 1 patient was not receiving any disease-modifying therapy. Among the 6 patients with PCS receiving disease-modifying therapy, the mean treatment duration of the current therapy was 6.3 years (range 4.6–8.0 years; n = 6). One patient with PCS was not receiving any therapy.

We did not collect information on the full treatment history over the course of the disease, but only on the current medication at the time of data collection.

With regard to categories our study participants, category III DMTs were most frequently used in MS (60/100, 60%), followed by category I (22/100, 22%) and category II (18/100, 18%) (for category details see Supplement Table 1).

Additionally, 34/107 (31.8%) of the study population reported limitations in walking ability, corresponding to an EDSS score of ≥ 4.0 .

3.2 Acute COVID-19 infection characteristics

The study cohort had a mean time between COVID-19 infection and questionnaire completion of 2.9 years (95% CI: 2.7–3.1, $n = 107$), with an average of 1.4 COVID-19 infections (95% CI: 1.2–1.5, $n = 107$). The most frequently reported symptoms of acute COVID-19 included cough (76/107, 71.0%), cold (71/107, 66.3%), and fever (58/107, 54.2%). Other common symptoms were sore throat (56/107, 52.3%) and fatigue (49/107, 46.7%). Additional symptoms included headache (49/107, 45.8%), pain (42/107, 39.2%), and dyspnea (14/107, 13.1%).

Prior to the COVID-19 infection, 39 participants (39/107, 36.4%) reported experiencing fatigue. After COVID-19, 9 participants (9/39, 23.1%) experienced an aggravation of fatigue. Regarding hospitalization, 9 participants (9/107, 8.4%) required hospital care, and only 1 participant (1/107, 0.9%) required intubation.

Regarding the worsening of the underlying disease, 20 participants (20/107, 18.7%) reported complete recovery of the previously worsened MS symptoms following COVID-19, whereas 5 participants (5/107, 4.7%) experienced incomplete recovery. An overview of the characteristics is provided in Table 1 (section A3).

In terms of antiviral treatments, 10 participants (10/107, 9.3%) were treated with Sotrovimab, while 7 participants (7/107, 6.5%) received Paxlovid. A positive PCR or antibody test was reported by 104 participants (104/107, 97.2%).

3.3 Subjective PCS symptoms reported by patients

Of the 107 participants, 7 (7/107, 6.5%) reported developing PCS. The most frequently reported symptoms of PCS were fatigue incl. post-exertional malaise (5/7, 71.4%), pain (4/7, 57.1%), and headache (3/7, 42.9%). Other symptoms included cough (2/7, 28.6%), dizziness (2/7, 28.6%), and autonomic dysfunction (3/7, 42.9%), which involved palpitations and orthostatic symptoms. Less commonly reported symptoms were sleeping disturbance (1/7, 14.3%), dyspnea (1/7, 14.3%), depressive mood with feelings of anxiety (1/7, 14.3%), anosmia/ageusia (1/7, 14.3%), and gastrointestinal symptoms (1/7, 14.3%). Further details are available in Table 1 (section A4).

Regarding the duration of PCS, 2 participants (2/7, 28.6%) reported symptoms lasting between 3-6 months, another 2 participants (2/7, 28.6%) experienced symptoms for 7-12 months, and 3 participants (3/7, 42.9%) had symptoms persisting for over 12 months.

A large portion of participants who reported to have developed PCS (5/7, 71.4%) sought a doctor's consultation for their PCS symptoms. In terms of therapy, 4 participants (4/7, 57.1%) underwent physiotherapy, while 1 participant (1/7, 14.3%) received ergotherapy or medication. The impact on daily life was considerable, with 3 participants (3/7, 42.9%) reporting incapacity to work, and 4 participants (4/7, 57.1%) reporting restrictions on their everyday activities.

3.4 Vaccination

Of the 107 participants, 85 (85/107, 79.4%) reported having received a COVID-19 vaccination. On average, participants received more than 2 vaccinations (n=88, 95% CI: 2.4–2.8). The most common vaccines administered were Moderna (40/85, 47.1%) and Pfizer/BioNTech (37/85, 43.5%), while 1 participant (1/85, 1.2%) received AstraZeneca, and 7 participants (7/85, 8.8%) had an unclear type of vaccination. Corresponding data are shown in Table 1 (section A5).

Regarding side effects, 33 participants (33/85, 38.8%) reported no side effects. The most frequent side effects were local reactions (39/85, 45.8%), followed by muscle pain (19/85, 22.3%), fatigue (15/85, 17.6%), and fever (13/85, 15.3%). Other reported side effects included headache (12/85, 14.1%) and worsening of MS symptoms (3/85, 3.5%). Only 1 participant (1/85, 1.2%) self-reported new symptoms compatible with an MS relapse following vaccination; the event was not clinically confirmed.

Among the 22 participants who did not vaccinate against SARS-CoV-2, the most common reasons included vaccination skepticism (16/22, 72.7%), fear of vaccines (5/22, 22.7%), and contraindications (1/22, 4.5%).

3.5 Comparison between patients with or without PCS

Patients with PCS (n = 7) were, on average, younger (33.7 years, 95% CI: 25.1-42.3 years) than those without the syndrome (43.4 years, 95% CI: 41.0–45.8 years). While this age difference was narrowly statistically significant (p = 0.037), it did not remain significant after adjustment for multiple testing using the Bonferroni procedure.

Additionally, individuals with PCS had a significantly higher mean number of COVID-19 infections (2.1, 95% CI: 1.93-3.0) compared to those without PCS (n = 100, 1.3,

95% CI: 1.2–1.4), with a p-value of 0.004, indicating that multiple infections may contribute to the development of PCS symptoms.

Furthermore, a higher proportion of patients with PCS experienced severe COVID-19 (28.6% [2/7]) compared to those without PCS (n = 100, 7.0% [7/100]), a difference that did not remain significant after adjustment for multiple testing using the Bonferroni procedure (p = 0.047). This result suggests that a history of more severe COVID-19 infections may serve as a risk factor for the development of PCS.

Regarding immunotherapy, a significant proportion of patients with PCS (n = 7) were on category I disease-modifying therapies (71.4% [5/7]), compared to just 17.0% [17/100] of patients without PCS (n = 100, p < 0.001).

Pre-existing fatigue prior to COVID-19 did not appear to have any significant influence on PCS outcomes, as no substantial difference was observed between the two groups in this regard. Lastly, while PCS patients (n = 7) were more likely to be unvaccinated at the time of infection (14.3% [1/7] vs. 61.0% [61/100]), this difference was not statistically significant. Details can be found in Table 2.

There was no significant difference in ambulatory limitation between patients with and without PCS. In our questionnaire, we did not specifically assess independent ambulatory status or the use of ambulatory assistance; instead, we operationalized reduced ambulation as EDSS > 4.

4. Discussion

Our analysis revealed five key findings. First, COVID-19 generally followed a mild and uncomplicated course in pwMS. Second, vaccination uptake among participants was high. Third, the incidence of PCS among pwMS was lower than expected compared to the general population, although the symptom profile was largely consistent. Fourth, a significantly higher proportion of individuals affected by PCS were receiving Category I DMTs, while fewer were on Category II or III therapies.

Regarding the acute phase of the COVID-19 infection, the majority of pwMS, in our cohort, experienced a mild course of COVID-19. Only 9% required hospitalization, and just one participant needed intubation. In 5 of 9 patients, infection likely coincided with the circulation of wild-type, Alpha, or Delta variants, and 6 of 9 patients were unvaccinated at the time of infection. The intubated patient was above 40 years of age, likely contracted the Delta variant, and had pre-existing ambulatory impairment.

These findings align with prior studies indicating that pwMS do not exhibit an increased risk of severe COVID-19 compared to the general population (Prosperini

et al., 2024; Richter et al., 2021). The presence of comorbidities, such as cardiovascular disease and depression may have influenced disease severity, though no clear pattern emerged. Additionally, only 23.4% of patients reported a worsening of MS symptoms during the COVID-19 infection, and most of them recovered without complications, suggesting that the infection did not universally exacerbate MS-related symptoms. This is consistent with previous reports indicating that COVID-19 may trigger transient symptom flares in MS but does not necessarily lead to long-term disease progression (Motolese et al., 2020).

One possible explanation for the generally mild course of the acute COVID-19 infection in our cohort is the high vaccination rate among participants. In our study, 79.4% (85/107) of participants received at least two doses of a COVID-19 vaccine. This supports existing evidence that vaccination plays a protective role in reducing the risk of severe disease in pwMS (Calcaterra et al., 2024). Vaccine-related side effects were generally mild, with the most common being local skin reactions, muscle pain, and fatigue. Only 3.5% of participants reported worsening MS symptoms post-vaccination, reinforcing the safety of vaccination in this population. While a small percentage stated experiencing MS relapse post-vaccination, these occurrences were rare and consistent with previous findings indicating a minimal risk of MS exacerbation following immunization (Stefanou et al., 2023).

21.6% of participants were unvaccinated which is considerably lower than that reported in a previous study assessing pneumococcal vaccination in pwMS, where 41.3% of patients refused the recommended vaccine (Diem et al., 2021). This suggests that COVID-19 vaccination acceptance among MS patients may be higher, potentially due to widespread public health campaigns and perceived higher risk of severe outcomes from SARS-CoV-2 infection. The COVID-19 vaccination rate in the general population in Switzerland is approximately 69.3% of the population having received at least one dose. The rate of people who have received a booster vaccination is around 55.6% (as of April 2025) (Official Data Collated by Our World in Data (2024); World Health Organisation (2025); Population Based on Various Sources (2024) – with Major Processing by Our World in Data, n.d.)

Regarding PCS, the incidence in our cohort was relatively low, with only 6.5% (7/107) of participants reporting persistent symptoms compared to the high prevalence of PCS in the general population (prevalence of 32% at 90 days and 49% at 120 days post-infection according to (Chen et al., 2022)). However, the symptom profile—characterized by fatigue, pain, and headache—mirrored that observed in broader studies (Chen et al., 2022). Notably, individuals with multiple COVID-19 infections and those who had more severe acute infections been at higher risk for developing PCS. This finding supports prior studies indicating that both repeated SARS-CoV-2 exposure and severe initial infections increase the likelihood of

prolonged symptoms in the general population (Cervia et al., 2022; Tsampasian et al., 2023).

It is noteworthy that most patients affected by PCS were treated with lower-intensity immunotherapies (category I), thus not being strongly immunosuppressed. These findings may suggest — albeit hypothetically — that more intensive immunosuppression could confer a protective effect against PCS. This hypothesis is consistent with findings from Bazylewicz et al. (2023), which suggest that immunomodulatory treatments may mitigate post-viral sequelae in MS patients (Bazylewicz et al., 2023). The mechanisms underlying this effect remain unclear but may involve dampening hyperinflammatory responses typically associated with post-viral conditions. However, it is important to note that patients with severe acute COVID-19 had a higher likelihood of developing PCS, regardless of their immunosuppressive therapy status. Specifically, 28.6% (2/7) of PCS patients had a history of severe COVID-19, compared to only 6.7% (7/100) of those without persistent symptoms. This highlights the role of acute disease severity as a major determinant of PCS outcomes (Prosperini et al., 2024).

Despite providing valuable insights into the course of COVID-19 and PCS in pwMS, this study has several limitations. First, the recruitment method via an online survey may have introduced selection bias, as individuals with more severe PCS symptoms or higher disability levels may have been less likely to participate. This could have led to an underestimation of PCS prevalence in the study population.

Second, the relatively small sample size ($n = 107$) limits the generalizability of the findings. Larger, multi-center studies are needed to confirm these observations. Furthermore, the absence of a control group without MS makes it difficult to determine whether the observed PCS prevalence is specific to MS patients or comparable to the general population.

Another limitation is the reliance on self-reported data, which introduces recall bias, particularly when assessing PCS symptoms retrospectively. Additionally, there was considerable variability in the time elapsed since the COVID-19 infection among participants, making it challenging to assess long-term outcomes consistently.

5. Conclusions

Our study identified five key findings: (1) COVID-19 generally followed an uncomplicated course in people with multiple sclerosis (pwMS), (2) vaccination among participants was high, (3) the incidence of post-COVID-19 syndrome (PCS) was lower than expected compared to the general population but demonstrated a symptom profile consistent with that described in the general population, (4) a

significantly higher proportion of individuals affected by PCS were receiving category I therapies, compared to those on categories II or III treatments.

Our findings contribute to the growing body of evidence on COVID-19 outcomes in MS patients, underscoring the importance of vaccination. The observation that immunosuppression may have a protective effect against PCS offers valuable insight into the role of immunotherapy in treating post-viral complications. This raises the question of whether targeted immunosuppressive strategies could be beneficial in PCS management. However, further research with larger cohorts and extended follow-up is needed to substantiate this hypothesis and refine therapeutic approaches in the context of PCS

Table description:

Table 1: Characteristics of patients

- A1: Population characteristics
- A2: MS characteristics
- A3: Acute COVID-19 infection characteristics
- A4: PCS symptoms (reported by patients, subjective)
- A5: Vaccination

Table 2: Comparison between patients with and without PCS

Supplement table 1: Categories of DMTs

Table 1: Characteristics of patients

A1) Population characteristics	
Age, years, mean (95% CI), n	42.7 (40.4-45.0), 107
Female sex, n (%)	71/107 (66.4)
Comorbidities, n (%)	
Migraine, n (%)	3/107 (2.8)
Psoriasis/Neurodermitis, n (%)	2/107 (1.9)
Depression, n (%)	3/107 (2.8)
Rheumatological disease n (%)	3/107 (2.8)
Cardiovascular disease, n (%)	9/107 (8.4)
Ocular disease, n (%)	1/107 (0.9)
Other medications, n (%)	
Vitamins, n (%)	54/107 (50.5)
psychiatric medication, n (%)	3/107 (2.8)
Anti spasticity drugs, n (%)	9/107 (8.4)
CBD/THC, n (%)	2/107 (1.9)
Fampridine, n (%)	4/107 (3.7)
Other immunotherapies, n (%)	1/107 (0.9)
blood thinners, n (%)	4/107 (3.7)

antihypertensive drugs, n (%)	11/107 (10.2)
lipid-lowering therapy, n (%)	5/107 (4.8)
Antidiabetic therapy, n (%)	5/107 (4.8)
contraceptives, n (%)	2/107 (1.9)
urology drugs, n (%)	2/107 (1.9)
levothyroxine, n (%)	2/107 (1.9)
A2) MS characteristics	
Diagnosis, n (%)	
RRMS, n (%)	90/107 (84.1)
PPMS, n (%)	12/107 (11.2)
SPMS, n (%)	5/107 (4.7)
DMTs, n (%)	
untreated, n (%)	7/107 (6.5)
Interferon/Glatiramer acetate, n (%)	3/107 (2.8)
Dimethyl fumarate, n (%)	17/107 (15.8)
Teriflunomide, n (%)	2/107 (1.9)
Sphingosid-1-Phosphate-Receptor, n (%)	7/107 (6.5)
Siponimod, n (%)	5/107 (4.7)
Cladribine, n (%)	6/107 (5.6)

Natalizumab, n (%)	6/107 (5.6)
Anti-CD20 monoclonal antibodies, n (%)	53/107 (49.5)
autologous hematopoietic stem cell transplantation, n (%)	1/107 (0.9)
Category MS-DMTs, n (%)	
Category I, n (%)	22/100 (22)
Category II, n (%)	18/100 (18)
Category III, n (%)	60/100 (60)
Ambulatory limitation, n (%)	34/107 (31.8)
A3) Acute COVID-19 infection characteristics	
Time between first COVID-19 and questionnaire, years, mean (95% CI), n	2.9 (2.7-3.1), 107
Presumed variant according to first infection date, n (%)	
Wild type (Wuhan-Hu-1)/ Alpha (B.1.1.7), n (%)	29/107 (26.4)
Delta (B.1.617.2), n (%)	17/107 (15.5)
Omicron, n (%)	64/107 (58.2)
Number of COVID 19, mean (95% CI), n	1.4 (1.2-1.5), 107
Symptoms of acute COVID-19, n (%)	

Headache, n (%)	49/107 (45.8)
Fever, n (%)	58/107 (54.2)
Dizziness, n (%)	4/107 (3.7)
Dyspnea, n (%)	14/107 (13.1)
Cough, n (%)	76/107 (71.0)
Cold, n (%)	71/107 (66.3)
Sore throat, n (%)	56/107 (52.3)
Pain, n (%)	42/107 (39.2)
Gastrointestinal symptoms, n (%)	3/107 (2.8)
Fatigue, n (%)	49/107 (46.7)
Anosmia, n (%)	5/107 (4.5)
Sleep disturbance, n (%)	4/107 (3.7)
Presence of Fatigue before COVID-19, n (%)	39/107 (36.4)
Aggravation of fatigue after COVID-19, n (%)	9/39 (23.1)
Hospitalization due to COVID-19, n (%)	9/107 (8.4)
Intubation due to COVID-19, n (%)	1/107 (0.9)

Worsening of MS symptoms due to COVID-19, n (%)	
With complete recovery, n (%)	20/107 (18.7)
With incomplete recovery, n (%)	5/107 (4.7)
Antiviral medications, n (%)	
Paxlovid, n (%)	7/107 (6.5)
Sotrovimab, n (%)	10/107 (9.3)
Positive SARS-CoV2 PCR or - Antibody Test, n (%)	104/107 (97.2)
A4) PCS symptoms	
Development of PCS, n (%)	7/107 (6.5)
Symptoms of PCS, n (%)	
Fatigue incl. post-exertional malaise, n (%)	5/7 (71.4)
Pain, n (%)	4/7 (57.1)
Headache, n (%)	3/7 (42.9)
Sleep disturbance (difficulty falling asleep and/or sleep maintenance insomnia), n (%)	1/7 (14.3)
Dyspnea, n (%)	1/7 (14.3)
Cough, n (%)	2/7 (28.6)
Depressive mood, feeling of anxiety, n (%)	1/7 (14.3)

Dizziness, n (%)	2/7 (28.6)
Anosmia/Ageusia, n (%)	1/7 (14.3)
Autonomic dysfunction (palpitations, orthostatic symptoms), n (%)	3/7 (42.9)
Gastrointestinal symptoms, n (%)	1/7 (14.3)
Duration of PCS, n (%)	
3-6 months, n (%)	2/7 (28.6)
7-12 months, n (%)	2/7 (28.6)
Over 12 months, n (%)	3/7 (42.9)
Doctor's consultation due to PCS, n (%)	5/7 (71.4)
Therapy of PCS, n (%)	
Physiotherapy, n (%)	4/7 (57.1)
Ergotherapy, n (%)	1/7 (14.3)
Medication, n (%)	1/7 (14.3)
Incapacity to work due to PCS, n (%)	3/7 (42.9)
Restrictions in everyday life due to PCS, n (%)	4/7 (57.1)
A5) Vaccination status	
Administration of COVID-19 vaccination, n (%)	85/107 (79.4)
Number of vaccinations, mean (95% CI), n	2.6 (2.4-2.8), 88

Type of COVID-19 vaccination, n (%)	
Pfizer/BioNTech, n (%)	37/85 (43.5)
Moderna, n (%)	40/85 (47.1)
Astra Zeneca, n (%)	1/85 (1.2)
Not clear, n (%)	7/85 (8.8)
Side Effect of vaccination, n (%)	
None, n (%)	33/85 (38.8)
Local reactions, n (%)	39/85 (45.8)
Fever, n (%)	13/85 (15.3)
Headache, n (%)	12/85 (14.1)
Muscle pain, n (%)	19/85 (22.3)
Fatigue, n (%)	15/85 (17.6)
Worsening of MS symptoms, n (%)	3/85 (3.5)
Self-reported MS relapses, n (%)	1/85 (1.2)
Reasons not being SARS-CoV2 vaccinated, n (%)	
fear of vaccines, n (%)	5/22 (22.7)
vaccination skepticism, n (%)	16/22 (72.7)
contraindication, n (%)	1/22 (4.5)

Table 2: Comparison between patients with and without PCS

Variable	Patients without PCS	Patients with PCS	p-value
Population characteristics			
Age, years, mean (95% CI), n	43.4 (41.0-45.8), 100	33.7 (25.1-42.3), 7	0.037
Female sex, n (%)	66/100 (66)	5/7 (71.4)	0.769
Comorbidities, n (%)	20/100 (20)	1/7 (14.3)	0.713
MS characteristics			
Diagnosis, n (%)			
RRMS	83/100 (83)	7/7 (100)	0.493
PPMS	12/100 (12)	0/7 (0)	
SPMS	5/100 (5)	0/7 (0)	
Ambulatory limitation	32/100 (32)	2/7 (28.6)	0.936
Naive, n (%)	6/100 (6)	1/7 (14.3)	0.391
Category I DMTs, n (%)	17/100 (17)	5/7 (71.4)	<0.001
Fatigue before COVID-19, n (%)	36/100 (36)	5/7 (71.4)	0.047
COVID-19 infection and vaccination characteristics			
Time between COVID19 and questionnaire, years, mean (95% CI), n	2.9 (2.7-3.1), 100	3.1 (1.9-4.2), 7	0.990
Number of infections, mean (95% CI), n	1.3 (1.2-1.4), 100	2.1 (1.3-3.0), 7	0.004
Severe COVID-19, n (%)	7/100 (7)	2/7 (28.6)	0.047

Antiviral medications, n (%)	17/100 (16.5)	1/7 (14.3)	0.905
Vaccinated at time point of COVID-19, n (%)	61/100 (61)	1/7 (14.3)	0.013

Author contributions

Deepak Sharma: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft; **Christian P. Kamm:** Writing - Review & Editing; **Robert Hoepner:** Writing - Review & Editing; **Iris-Katharina Penner:** Writing - Review & Editing; **Thomas Nyffeler:** Writing - Review & Editing; **Lara Diem:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration, Formal analysis

Funding sources

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or non-profit sectors.

References

- Bazylewicz, M., Gudowska-Sawczuk, M., Mroczko, B., Kochanowicz, J., & Kułakowska, A. (2023). COVID-19: The Course, Vaccination and Immune Response in People with Multiple Sclerosis: Systematic Review. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, *24*(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/IJMS24119231>
- Calcaterra, V., Zanelli, S., Foppiani, A., Verduci, E., Benatti, B., Bollina, R., Bombaci, F., Brucato, A., Cammarata, S., Calabrò, E., Cirnigliaro, G., Della Torre, S., Dell'osso, B., Moltrasio, C., Marzano, A. V., Nostro, C., Romagnuolo, M., Trotta, L., Savasi, V., ... Zuccotti, G. (2024). Long COVID in Children, Adults, and Vulnerable Populations: A Comprehensive Overview for an Integrated Approach. *Diseases (Basel, Switzerland)*, *12*(5). <https://doi.org/10.3390/DISEASES12050095>
- Cervia, C., Zurbuchen, Y., Taeschler, P., Ballouz, T., Menges, D., Hasler, S., Adamo, S., Raeber, M. E., Bächli, E., Rudiger, A., Stüssi-Helbling, M., Huber, L. C., Nilsson, J., Held, U., Puhan, M. A., & Boyman, O. (2022). Immunoglobulin signature predicts risk of post-acute COVID-19 syndrome. *Nature Communications*, *13*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/S41467-021-27797-1>
- Chen, C., Hauptert, S. R., Zimmermann, L., Shi, X., Fritsche, L. G., & Mukherjee, B. (2022). Global Prevalence of Post COVID-19 Condition or Long COVID: A Meta-Analysis and Systematic Review. *The Journal of Infectious Diseases*, *226*(9), 1593–1607. <https://doi.org/10.1093/INFDIS/JIAC136>
- Diem, L., Friedli, C., Chan, A., Salmen, A., & Hoepner, R. (2021). Vaccine Hesitancy in Patients With Multiple Sclerosis. *Neurology Neuroimmunology & Neuroinflammation*, *8*(3). <https://doi.org/10.1212/NXI.0000000000000991>
- Ford, N. D., Slaughter, D., Edwards, D., Dalton, A., Perrine, C., Vahratian, A., & Saydah, S. (2023). Long COVID and Significant Activity Limitation Among Adults, by Age — United States, June 1–13, 2022, to June 7–19, 2023. *MMWR. Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, *72*(32), 866–870. <https://doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.mm7232a3>
- Januel, E., Hajage, D., Labauge, P., Maillart, E., De Sèze, J., Zephir, H., Pelletier, J., Guilloton, L., Bensa, C., Heinzlef, O., Casez, O., Biotti, D., Bourre, B., Vukusic, S., Maurousset, A., Berger, E., Laplaud, D., Lebrun-Frénay, C., Dubessy, A. L., ... Louapre, C. (2023). Association Between Anti-CD20 Therapies and COVID-19 Severity Among Patients With Relapsing-Remitting and Progressive Multiple Sclerosis. *JAMA Network Open*, *6*(6), E2319766. <https://doi.org/10.1001/JAMANETWORKOPEN.2023.19766>
- Kamm, C. P., Uitdehaag, B. M., & Polman, C. H. (2014). Multiple Sclerosis: Current Knowledge and Future Outlook. *European Neurology*, *72*(3–4), 132–141. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000360528>
- Liu, N., Yu, W., Sun, M., Zhang, W., Zhou, D., Sun, J., & Wang, M. X. (2023). Outcome of COVID-19 Infection in Patients With Multiple Sclerosis Who Received Disease-Modifying Therapies: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Clinical Neurology (Seoul, Korea)*, *19*(4), 381. <https://doi.org/10.3988/JCN.2022.0348>
- Montani, D., Savale, L., Noel, N., Meyrignac, O., Colle, R., Gasnier, M., Corruble, E., Beurnier, A., Jutant, E. M., Pham, T., Lecoq, A. L., Papon, J. F., Figueiredo, S., Harrois, A., Humbert, M., & Monnet, X. (2022). Post-acute COVID-19 syndrome. *European Respiratory Review*, *31*(163). <https://doi.org/10.1183/16000617.0185-2021>
- Motolese, F., Rossi, M., Albergo, G., Stelitano, D., Villanova, M., Di Lazzaro, V., & Capone, F. (2020). The Psychological Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on People With Multiple Sclerosis. *Frontiers in Neurology*, *11*, 580507. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FNEUR.2020.580507/FULL>

- Nalbandian, A., Sehgal, K., Gupta, A., Madhavan, M. V., McGroder, C., Stevens, J. S., Cook, J. R., Nordvig, A. S., Shalev, D., Sehwat, T. S., Ahluwalia, N., Bikdeli, B., Dietz, D., Der-Nigoghossian, C., Liyanage-Don, N., Rosner, G. F., Bernstein, E. J., Mohan, S., Beckley, A. A., ... Wan, E. Y. (2021). Post-acute COVID-19 syndrome. *Nature Medicine*, 27(4), 601. <https://doi.org/10.1038/S41591-021-01283-Z>
- Official data collated by *Our World in Data* (2024); *World Health Organisation* (2025); *Population based on various sources* (2024) – with major processing by *Our World in Data*. (n.d.). Retrieved May 5, 2025, from <https://ourworldindata.org/coronavirus>
- Oliver-Mas, S., Matias-Guiu, J. A., Delgado-Alonso, C., Cuevas, C., Alcalá Ramírez del Puerto, J. M., López-Carbonero, J. I., Matias-Guiu, J., & Diez-Cirarda, M. (2025). Differential Fatigue Profile in Patients with Post-COVID Condition, Fibromyalgia, and Multiple Sclerosis. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 14(3), 952. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm14030952>
- Pierce, J. D., Shen, Q., Cintron, S. A., & Hiebert, J. B. (2022). Post-COVID-19 Syndrome. *Nursing Research*, 71(2), 164–174. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NNR.0000000000000565>
- Post COVID-19 condition (Long COVID). (n.d.). Retrieved June 7, 2024, from <https://www.who.int/europe/news-room/fact-sheets/item/post-covid-19-condition>
- Prosperini, L., Arrambide, G., Celius, E. G., Goletti, D., Killestein, J., Kos, D., Lavorgna, L., Louapre, C., Sormani, M. P., Stastna, D., Ziemssen, T., & Di Filippo, M. (2024). COVID-19 and multiple sclerosis: challenges and lessons for patient care. *The Lancet Regional Health. Europe*, 44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LANEPE.2024.100979>
- Richter, D., Faissner, S., Bartig, D., Tönges, L., Hellwig, K., Ayzenberg, I., Krogias, C., & Gold, R. (2021). Multiple sclerosis is not associated with an increased risk for severe COVID-19: a nationwide retrospective cross-sectional study from Germany. *Neurological Research and Practice*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/S42466-021-00143-Y>
- Salmen, A., Marti, S., Hoepner, A. G. F., Chan, A., & Hoepner, R. (2023). The impact of immunotherapies on COVID-19 case fatality rates during the US vaccination campaign: a multidisciplinary open data analysis using FDA Adverse Event Reporting System and Our World in Data. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 14, 1186404. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2023.1186404>
- Stefanou, M. I., Palaiodimou, L., Theodorou, A., Christodoulou, M. V., Tzartos, J. S., Tzanetakos, D., Kitsos, D., Chondrogianni, M., Zouvelou, V., Dardiotis, E., Tzavellas, E., Syrigou, E., Benetou, V., Paraskevas, G. P., Tsiodras, S., Tsvigoulis, G., & Giannopoulos, S. (2023). Safety of COVID-19 vaccines in multiple sclerosis: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Multiple Sclerosis (Houndmills, Basingstoke, England)*, 29(4–5), 585–594. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13524585221150881>
- Tsampsian, V., Elghazaly, H., Chattopadhyay, R., Debski, M., Naing, T. K. P., Garg, P., Clark, A., Ntatsaki, E., & Vassiliou, V. S. (2023). Risk Factors Associated With Post-COVID-19 Condition: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *JAMA Internal Medicine*, 183(6). <https://doi.org/10.1001/JAMAINTERNMED.2023.0750>
- Wenzel, M., Berthele, A., & Hemmer, B. (2022). Aktuelle leitliniengerechte Therapie der Multiplen Sklerose. *InFo Neurologie + Psychiatrie*, 24(5), 44–53. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s15005-022-2307-3>

Verdankung und/oder Widmung

Mein Dank gilt meinem Doktorvater Prof. Dr. med. Christian Kamm für die kompetente fachliche Betreuung. Ebenso danke ich Frau Dr. med. Lara Diem für die wertvolle und empathische Anleitung.

Meiner Verlobten Jasmin gilt mein herzlicher Dank für ihre Geduld und Unterstützung in dieser Zeit. Meiner Familie danke ich für ihren beständigen Rückhalt und ihr Verständnis.

Curriculum Vitae

Dr. medic. (RO) Deepak Sharma

15.06.1995	Geboren in Banga, Indien
1998 - 2007	St. Soldier Senior Secondary Public School Banga, Indien
2007 - 2008	Hauptschule Lohmar, Deutschland
2008 - 2014	Gymnasium Lohmar, Deutschland
28.06.2014	Abschluss Abitur
2015 – 2021	Studium der Humanmedizin an der University of Medicine and Pharmacy Timisoara, Rumänien
12.07.2021	Abschluss des Medizinstudiums (Titel: Dr. medic. / M.D.)
10.11.2021	Ausstellung Anerkennungsbestätigung MEBEKO
11/2021 – 11/2022	Assistenzarzt Allgemeine Innere Medizin, Spital Herisau AR
Seit 01/2023	Assistenzarzt Neurologie, Luzerner Kantonsspital LU